

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ERDMANN****FIRST NAME: DANIEL****PROGRAM CODE: HABILITATION****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: PROF. GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium.

The author used the following software: MSWord for Mac 2011 on macOS Mojave.

STUDYING AT EUCLID

1) INTRODUCTION

At the very beginning of one's academic career, EUCLID offers an initial course on International Academic and Professional Paper Writing. This first period of the course prepares the student in a detailed way to become familiar with the writing standards expected by EUCLID and the academic world in general. The provided document discusses topics such as essay writing, the purpose of style, and how to avoid plagiarism.

2) STARTING FROM SCRATCH

Writing academic papers, articles and reports can easily be an overwhelming task, specially if the field itself is underestimated due to its complexity. The crucial point for any academic writing and research is the creation of the starting-point, namely the proper question under investigation. Once having this formulated, reading and selecting text parts starts making sense (EUCLID 2015, 3).

Not only for native speakers but specially for non-native speakers the English language offers several details that an academic writer needs to stress one's attention to. Such a circumstance is for example the accurate use of the apostrophes, maybe one of the most frequently committed failures. Getting it straight, the apostrophe's positioning depends on whether the noun is singular or plural (EUCLID 2015, 47). The course material further shares light on the correct use of *that* and *which*, (EUCLID 2015, 48), and on another tricky point, at least for non-native speakers, namely the definition of the accurate use of *I* and *me* (EUCLID 2015, 50-51).

3) EUCLID'S STANDARDS

The majority of the course material covers the crucial point(s) of following a specific, and previously provided, style and implementing the correct citation rules. Of course, plagiarism is a common problem in creative work in general, but by understanding once the importance of citation, the writer may avoid a high degree of plagiarism (EUCLID 2015, 12).

The very basis of all writing is the commonly followed style, specifically when we talk about journal articles and mutually worked on book publications. It is mandatory that all contributors follow the same concept (EUCLID 2015, 52). EUCLID asks its students to mainly use the Turabian Style (EUCLID 2015, 52). Topics that are dealt with are the use of abbreviations, capitalization, italics, etc. To guarantee a correct and mutual usage, students are asked to make use of the EUCLID template (EUCLID 2015, 6).

The course material states that Plagiarism is a use of content without giving credit to its source EUCLID (2015, 9). This is basically pretty easy to avoid by simply being fair enough to honor other person's ideas, thoughts, and work in general. The point is that authors frequently fail to be creative enough to have proper ideas to accurately work and think for themselves. In order to make people understand that giving credit is not that difficult at all, the document discusses how to deal with endnotes, footnotes, and bibliographies (EUCLID 2015, 75-77).

4) UK VS. US ENGLISH

Having learned UK English in school, I switched to US English when I started being in contact with global peers, partners, and clients. To me, it is just like the international acceptance of the US Dollar being a currency of comparison. Being familiar with the US English makes sense as it is the more frequently used form of both (EUCLID 2015, 52-54).

5) CONCLUSION

It is needless to say that content such as provided in period one of ACA-401 is always of crucial help, specially the details are often hard to remember and need a constant refreshment. The setting of the course material is easy to follow and is a great source to work with on a practical daily basis.

REFERENCES

Euclid University. 2015. "ACA-401 Coursepack Period 1." Accessed May 4, 2021.
<https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401-period-1/>.

Cleenerwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
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